
Antibiotic Susceptibility Pattern of Bacteria Isolates in Honey from Locations within the Tamale Metropolis of the Northern Region of Ghana

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Abstract In Tamale, honey is used as a therapeutic agent for the treatment of both humans and animal infections, for religious ceremonies as well as a food source. News about adulteration of honey from the retail outlets has gained media attention and such messages have serious repercussions on the good image of honey. Notwithstanding, antimicrobial resistance of foodborne microorganisms constitute a serious public health hazard, thus the current study. The bacteria quality of the 25-honey sampled from the different retail outlets within the Tamale metropolis was determined using the method described by the Association of Official Analytical Chemists (AOAC, 2001). The frequency of bacteria occurrences are as follows; *Enterobacter* spp. 15 (60%); *Streptococcus* spp. 14 (56%); *Staphylococcus* spp. 12 (48%) and *E. coli* 10 (40%). The least pH, 4.43 ± 0.11 SD value was recorded for samples obtained from the retailers outside the main Tamale central market whereas the highest pH value, 4.54 ± 0.07 SD was from retailers inside the central market. Antibiotic susceptibility pattern of the bacteria isolates was determined using the Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method with EUCAST interpretation. All the bacterial isolates showed resistance to at least two (2) of the antibiotics used in this study. The degree of resistance of isolates to the antibiotics ranges from 20 to 100%. The detection of antibiotic resistant organisms is a cause for concern as the consumption of honey containing these resistant organisms may prolong the treatment of food-borne diseases.

Keywords Honey, Antibiotic resistance, Tamale metropolis

Introduction

Honey is said to be the sweetest food on earth often called the liquid gold of nature, a unique product in terms of its nourishment and healing properties [1]. Worldwide, honey is considered as one of the gift of nature with varying functional applications and uses [2].

Nonetheless, microbiological quality analysis of different honey has revealed that some honey harbors certain microorganisms and that honey in spite of its usefulness may serve as a reservoir for microorganisms [3]. In attempt to trace the source of contamination, Popa *et al* [4], mentioned the processing area as well as the machines and containers used in the manufacturing of honey as some of the sources of microbial contamination.

In recent times, antibiotics has also been found as a contaminant of honey. Alippi *et al* [5], emphasized on antibiotics employed in beekeeping or honey production as the sources of antibiotics in honey. The continuous use of antibiotics as veterinary drugs and as a growth promoter in beekeeping has instigated a selective pressure and with the resulting emergence of resistant strains of bacteria [6-7]. The emergence of multi-drug resistant strains

results in the persistence of pathogen in food processing environment which in turn extends treatment of disease conditions, increase in hospitalization rates as well as rise in mortality rate in humans and animals [8].

Since there is a high perception of adulteration practice by market sellers whilst antimicrobial resistance of foodborne pathogens constitutes a great threat to public health thus the need to investigate the bacteriological quality and the antibiotic susceptibility or sensitivity profile of bacteria isolates in honey from retail outlets of different locations within the Tamale metropolis of the Northern region of Ghana.

Materials and Methods

Source of honey samples

A total of 25 different honey samples (i.e. 5 samples per market) were collected from market sellers in five different markets within the Tamale metropolis of the Northern region of Ghana. These five (5) markets (Aboabo, Nyohini, Nyankpala, Tamale central, and Lamashegu market) were selected based on consumers/buyers' perceptions of adulteration by the market sellers.

The samples were categorized on the basis of location which is the market from which it was collected. Samples were collected in sterile bottles and transported to the lab in an ice chest containing ice cubes. Three (3) sets of analysis was carried out: the first was the determination of pH; the second was microbial analysis; and the third was the antimicrobial susceptibility/sensitivity testing. All three (3) sets of analyses were carried out in the Spanish laboratory complex of the University for Development Studies, Nyankpala campus.

Determination of pH

The pH of all the honey samples was determined based on the procedures prescribed by AOAC [9]. Five (5) g of each honey sample was measured and dissolved in a 15ml of deionized water in a volumetric flask. The pH was then recorded using a pH meter (Crison pH meter Basic 20).

Microbial Analysis

Microbial analysis of all 25 honey samples was carried out using the method described in the Compendium of methods for the Microbiological Examination of Foods [10].

All the media (MacConkey Oxoid Ltd., Basingstoke, Hampshire, England; Nutrient Agar Techno Pharmchem, India; Salmonella Shigella Techno Pharmchem, India; and Mueller-Hinton (MH) agar Techno Pharmchem, India) were prepared according to the manufacturer's instructions.

Ten (10) g of the honey sample was weighed using an electronic scale (Sartorius CP2245) and homogenized in a 90ml of 0.1 peptone water (Oxoid, Basingstoke, UK). Twenty (20) ml of each of the sterilized media was poured into sterilized petri dishes and allow to cool for solidification. Hundred (100) μ l of the prepared sample was inoculated on the surface of the respective agar plates upon solidification. Inoculated samples on Nutrient agar plates and SS agar plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 to 48hrs whereas that of MacConkey agar plates were incubated at 44.5 °C using the JP-Selecta digital incubator.

Identification and Confirmation of Enumerated Microorganisms

After 24-48 hours of incubation, distinct colonies were streaked on a freshly prepared nutrient agar and incubated at 37 °C. This was carried out to obtain pure cultures for identification and confirmation purposes. Biochemical tests such as the Gram stain, catalase test, citrate test and oxidase test were carried out to identify and confirm the isolates.

Antibiotic Testing

Antibiotic sensitivity/susceptibility test was performed using the Kirby-Bauer's disc diffusion method. Antibiotic discs (Axiom Laboratories, India) used for Gram positive isolates were different from that of Gram-negative isolates. Also, the European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) breakpoints tables for

interpretation of minimum inhibition zone diameter version 5.0 was used to determine the susceptibility/sensitivity of the isolates.

Statistical Analysis

Data generated from the study was computed in Excel (Microsoft office 13) and analyzed using XSTAT. The results were presented in tables and graphs.

Results and Discussion

pH of Honey Samples

Figure 1: pH of the honey samples from the different retail outlets

The pH of the honey samples ranged from $4.43 \pm 0.11SD$ to $4.54 \pm 0.07SD$ (Figure 1). There was no significant difference among the values recorded for pH of the honey samples from the different retail outlets.

The results on pH of the honey samples from the different outlets showed that the samples were within the acceptable range of pH specified by the Codex Alimentarius Commission [11]. Also, they were within the acceptable range of between 3.6 and 5.6 reported by Adebisi *et al* [12]. Nonetheless, the findings on pH of all the 25 honey sampled from the different outlets conforms well with that of Nyau, [13]. Lawal [14], mentioned that the pH of honey is an important parameter which cannot be overlooked; since it has great influence on its microbial characteristics as well as its shelf-life.

The physicochemical characteristics of honey makes it unfavorable for microorganisms to thrive. However, honey should not be considered as a sterile environment [15], as such the enumeration of certain microorganisms should not be seen as a strange phenomenon.

Occurrence of Bacteria Isolates

Table 1: Frequency of bacteria isolates in honey

Bacteria	No. of Samples (+)	Percentage	No. of Samples (-)	Percentage	Total
Staphylococcus spp.	12	48%	13	52%	25(100%)
Streptococcus spp.	14	56%	11	44%	25(100%)
Shigella spp.	0	0%	25	100%	25(100%)
Salmonella spp.	0	0%	25	100%	25(100%)
Escherichia coli	10	40%	15	60%	25(100%)
Enterobacter spp.	15	60%	10	40%	25(100%)

** Positive occurrence (+) ** Negative occurrence (-)

E. coli and *Enterobacter spp.* are determinants of sanitary conditions, thus their presence in honey indicates human and environmental contaminations [16]. Since *E. coli* and *Enterobacter spp.* are one of the predominant food pathogens, their absence in 15(60%) and 10(40%) of the respective sample gives credence to the quality of the sampling locations as well as the respective sellers. This finding is in line with the findings of Onyeze *et al* [17], who isolated *E. coli* and *Enterobacter spp.* from honey sampled from three different locations in Enugu state of Nigeria.

Staphylococcus spp. and *Streptococcus spp.* were detected in 12(48%) and 14(56%) respectively. Laaberki and Dworkin [18], mentioned that the detection of these microorganism particularly *Streptococcus spp.* in honey samples might be due to the fact these bacteria are able to form spores which confers them resistance to harsh environment. Adjaloo *et al* [16], reported the detection of *Streptococcus spp.* in honey sampled from production sites in Drobo and Berekum. Also, Adadi and Obeng [19], recorded microbial load of *Staphylococcus spp.* and *Streptococcus spp.* in honey produced from the Tamale metropolis.

Notwithstanding, the results on *Shigella spp.* contradicts the findings of Adadi and Obeng (2016), who recorded high microbial load of *Shigella spp.* in honey obtained directly form honey producers within the Tamale metropolis. This is because there was no detection of *Shigella spp.* for all the 25 honey samples analyzed. Nonetheless, results for *Salmonella spp.* conforms so well with aforementioned researchers since *Salmonella spp.* was not detected in both cases.

The detection of bacteria from some of the retail outlets may be attributed to the handling and adulteration of such honey because a well-preserved honey provides unfavorable environment for the survival of bacteria. The practice of adulteration by market sellers in order to obtain a higher profit affects the acidic nature of honey which in turn provides room for microbial growth.

Antibiotic susceptibility pattern of bacteria isolates

Figure 2: Antibiotic resistance profile of Gram-negative isolates

As mentioned earlier, the use of antibiotics in beekeeping and the subsequent detection of these antibiotics in honey results to the damaging effect to the good image of honey. However, not only does the presence of antibiotics renders a bad image to honey but it also results in microorganisms developing resistance to these antibiotics.

In this study, all four isolates of bacteria showed resistance to at least two of the tested antibiotics. *E. coli* and *Enterobacter spp.* were both 100 % resistant to Ampicillin, Tetracycline and Chloramphenicol (figure 2). However, *E. coli* isolates were 100% susceptible to Co-trimoxazole whereas *Enterobacter spp.* was 100 % resistant to Co-trimoxazole. Tetracycline worked effectively against *Streptococcus spp.* whilst *Staphylococcus spp.* showed 100 % resistance (Figure 3). Both isolates were however 100 % resistant to Amoxicillin and Lincomycin.

Figure 3: Antibiotics resistance profile of Gram-positive isolates

Global report on antibiotics susceptibility/sensitivity test on honey are those that suggest the antibacterial effect of honey against some selected isolates. Therefore, to isolate resistant strains of bacteria from honey is a cause for concern since this suggest that these bacteria have bridged both the antibacterial potency of honey and that of the synthetic antibiotics. It is recommended further that attention should be drawn to the study of antimicrobial resistance pattern of microorganisms isolated from honey.

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